

TYPES OF UZBEK BREAD

Latipova Umida Usmanovna ¹

¹ UzSWLU, base doctoral student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5555612>

MAQOLA TARIXI

Qabul qilindi: 21-sentabr 2021
Ma'qullandi: 25-sentabr 2021
Chop etildi: 30-sentabr 2021

KALIT SO'ZLAR

*bread, cuisine, oven,
traditional, dishes,
hospitality, table, taste,
popular*

ANNOTATSIYA

This article analyzes the national uzbek cuisine such is plover, bread, manti. It also gives some important information how to make different kind of uzbek bread. Uzbek people are very hospitality.

Uzbekistan is known not only for its sacred sites and architectural monuments, but also for its unique and national cuisine. Not only its cuisine, but various types of bread also amazing and incredible. It is impossible to imagine the Uzbek table without bread. That is why bread is sacred and holy. Not only, but its crust also sacred for Uzbek people and do their best not to discard it. We can see various types and forms of bread depending on the nationality, location and religion of a man or a woman who bakes it. As we are from [Uzbekistan](#), I consider it's our essential duty to let other people know about unique Uzbek bread – “Issik non” or a hot patir.

In my opinion, the breads of Uzbekistan should be considered the eighth wonder of the world. It takes hard work for wheat to come to the table as bread from the grain state. So Uzbek people decorate bread like tapestries that reflect the lives of the

people who make and consume them and often mimicking colorful, intricate caftans and the ornate Islamic geometric patterns that decorate homes and places of worship, these breads are inseparable from daily life—imbued with meaning way beyond physical nourishment.

Anyone, who has ever tasted Uzbek hot pastil, will stay in love forever with this miracle with a crisp, divinely supple, odorous flesh and crumbs of sesame, exploding on the teeth with a unique flavor. Moreover, in case when it has just begun dawning in the street and you hold a piala (cup) of a hot odoriferous tea in your hands, there is also a dish of the freshest clotted cream (a kind of dense cream) on the table, nothing will not be able to stop you from such unbelievable, incridible delicious, remarkably nutritious and the most proper breakfast in the whole world.

The types of bread vary in size, shape, ingredients and taste. Bread is the main food product, prepared from water, flour and yeast, mixed and baked in the oven. You can eat bread in the form of flat bread, in the form of small buns, in the form of baguettes or in the form of baking. The type of bread depends on the color (white, brown or whole grain) and any additional flavor used tiger bread differs from ordinary bread by taste, because rice paste is used before cooking. We must explore the names of these brands to enlarge the vocabulary of food in English. In fact, it is a unique gift of the creator of Uzbek bread in food products. The preparation and consumption of bakery products constitute a separate page for the Uzbek people. Bread is very glorified. It has become a tradition to meet great guests with bread and salt. The first to put bread products on the table is a sign of its greatness.

Food products are a means of providing the body with well enough energy and heat. At the same time, it supplies the necessary substances for both physical and mental development of the organism. Useful nutrition should have concentrated many of the necessary elements that serve to maintain health. We know that in order to maintain strength, it is necessary for the body not only to eat, but also to have nutrients that are able to meet its specific requirements. As far as we know, it is made from whole-wheat flour. Bread can be added to various dishes or eaten by itself. When products are consumed, the substances absorbed in the body are oxidized, which will be of benefit to those who live an active lifestyle and perform serious, harmful, heavy physical labor should also be rich of vitamins and natural in this case.

In Uzbekistan, in general, many residents of Central Asia had different types of baking method of baking. Accordingly, depending on the bread in the oven, pan bread, gas-oven bread, flour tortillas are divided into such types as wheat bread, barley bread, corn and white oatmeal bread. Depending on the technology of preparation in Uzbek cooking, obi consists of bread, gijda bread, patir bread, shirmay bread, sometimes lojhira is also included in a separate technological type. In the preparation of Obi bread (which means Persian — water bread) is mainly carried out by adding yeast and salt to the dough wheat flour. In Obi Bread, the dough is relatively soft, the dough piece is small (about 200 g) is characteristic. In the method of Gijda is also carried out by adding yeast and salt to the wheat flour, and then smells longer. In the oven, the dough becomes stiff and the bread is rolled out thick. During the period of development, demand for bread and its varieties is increasing, as other directions have developed. As a result of the fact that bread is the symbol of the highest hospitality and excellence, the skill of bakers has been growing for centuries, and technological methods have been improved, dozens of varieties of bread have been created in obi, gijda, patir and shirmay.

I'd prefer mention that in Uzbekistan, according to their sacred national tradition, bread is never cut with a knife. At first, the bread will break by hand and distribute it from several pieces to the opposite of each guest. On the day of marriage of married young people, bread is broken according to a special tradition, so that their family relations are always sweet and forever, lasting. This means that the great respect for bread and bakery products in the country was formed in ancient times; bread in the

culture of the Uzbek people took a very large and unique place.

References:

1. Karim Maxmudov, O'zbek taomlari. 336 bet, Toshkent 1977
1. Pol Breg, To'g'ri ovqatlanish. 334 bet, Toshkent 2014
2. "The noodle-rich cuisine of Uzbekistan", The Village Voice, Dining, 19 January 1999.